

WORDS WHOSE MEANING HAS EXPANDED IN "MAHBUB UL-QULUB".

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Abstract. In this article, the expansion of meaning in A. Navoi's work "Mahbub ul-Qulub" is discussed, from the meaning that first expressed a narrow reality to a wider reality later.

Key words: lexicon, polysemantics, monosemantics, semantic structure, figurative meaning, ancient Turkic sources.

This process is the shift of a single-meaning word towards polysematicity in the lexicon of the work "Mahbub ul-Qulub", its enrichment with colorful new meanings, expansion of the semantic structure of polysemous words, mobile meaning. occurred due to the formation of nos. For example, the word aç, which means "hungry, hungry", was originally expressed in Turfon texts: Yaliñ boğazi todmaz aç yoriyur – uning och tomog‘i to‘ymas, doimo och yuradi (DTS,3) This term continued its original meaning even in the first records of the old Turkic language: Aç ne yemäs, toq ne temäs (MK,1,108). It can be seen in "Qisasi Rabguzi" that the lexeme was still in use in the later period: Bu aç xalāyiqğa yüzüñni körgüzgil (93r11). The studied source gives the meanings of "hungry, not full", "poor, impoverished": Bermasang ochdur, bersang to‘q (MQ,73); Birta o‘tmakni ikki bo‘lub, yarmin bir ochg‘a berganni saxiy de (MQ,59). The verb kat- is mentioned in ancient Turkic language records in the meanings "to thicken", "to stick, to stick", "to join" (DTS, 432). In "Devonu Lugotit Turk" it is prominent in the meanings of "to mix", "to mix" (MK,II,341), "to laugh" (MK,I,338). In the work "Mahbub ul-Qulub" it is written in the following meanings:

1) to harden ...makes the dull eye cry (MQ, 62);

2) **deliver**: Yaxshilarg‘a erishmak — itni poklar chergasiga qotti (MQ,62);

3) **join**: Fisq shumlug‘idin o‘zingni yaxshilardin huratma va yomonlar orasig‘a qotma (MQ,90);

4) **mix**: Ulki chin so‘zni yolg‘ong‘a qotar, durri saminni najosatg‘a otar (MQ,93);

5) **mix, beat**: Va goh xayrot ahlig‘a o‘zumni qottim va har nav‘ xayr buq‘alari tuzattim..(MQ,8);

6) **add**: Muzd uchun siym olibki, molig‘a qotar dinini dunyog‘a sotar (MQ,18).

In the 10th century monument "Golden Light", "Kutadgu Bilig", "Devonu Lugatit Turk", "Hibat ul-Haqaiq" works, the term "elig" means "hand": Ötrü eliglärin örü kötürüp... then raising his hands up (DTS,170). The mentioned lexeme is found in the analyzed source in the phonetic forms of ilik/ilig/ilki/ilgi and represents several senses: "hand"...ul favokih jonidin har ne iliklarig‘a tutsa ko‘zlarig‘a surtub... (MQ,42); "finger, paw"...shukrdurkim, ilging bahli panjasidek nokor yo‘q va andin sanga ozor yo‘q (MQ,96); Iyd oqshomi tifi ilgida chapu rost hino (MQ,78); "horn": Chinor ilgi xolilig‘idin biyikligiga ne nuqson va tufroqqa nihon ganjlari bila ne ulvi shon (MQ,59); "profession, profession" Izzat ahliki mazallatqa tushti san‘at ilgi yo‘qturu va savol tili (MQ,83); “bilak” Shayx dastgirlikka qo‘lin uzotti, ilkin tutub chekti, bahr sohilig‘a otti (MQ,88). Also, this word is reflected in the composition of phrases and expressions and served to mean the following meanings: "get out of hand": Dono ilikdin borg‘ondin so‘z aytmas, o‘tgan yigitlik orzu bila qaytmas (MQ,94); "to follow, to follow": Bas o‘zni yaxshilar orasida yashurg‘on va alar etagiga ilik urg‘on yaxshiroqdur (MQ,91); "to be engaged in some work": Hunarmand qoshida behunar ilik tebratmasa, ayb tuhmatin anga taqar (MQ,80); "give up": Quloq karligidur molo, ya‘ni mas‘mu‘otdin ilik tortmog‘lig‘dur barcha nomashru‘otdin (MQ,38); "to meet" ...mundoq komgorliq ilikka tushsa, nihoniy g‘am-u mehnatda hamroz va hamdaming bo‘lg‘ay (MQ,33); “olib kelmoq”: Muqbilning iligin tutub shaharg‘a qaytti (MQ,45). In ancient Turkic memoirs and Yusuf Khos Hajib's epic "Qutadgu bilig", the verb kurut/kurit- means "to dry" (DTS, 470). In Mahmud Koshgari's "Devoni" it is used in the meanings of "to dry", "to stop

from developing, to stop from bruising": kun to'nig' quritti – quyosh to'nni quritti (MQ,II,352); Bu yer ol telim uzum quritg'an – bu odam ko'p uzumlarni quritgan (MQ,I,470) This lexeme is found in "Mahbub ul-Qulub" in four different forms, that is, the range of meaning is expanded: "to dry": Har fisqkim, pushaymonliq o'tin yurutqay, ul o't tardomanliq oludalig'in qurutqay (MQ,74); "to lose, to ruin": Shag'ol jonibin tutmoq — tovuq tuxmin qurutmoqdur (MQ,66); "zoe ketkazmoq, bebahra qilmoq": ...ul birin yutmoqdin zahr yutma, bu birin sochmoqdin nasling tuxmin qurutma (MQ,90); "to stop growing" Bashar jinsidin vafo ko'z tutma va xirad naxlin fosid xayol samumi bila qurutma (MQ,91). The time was first mentioned in Yusuf Khos Hajib's epic "Kutadgu Bilig" in the term "time, era": Bu Buğraxan vaqti ičrä anı/yemä xan tilinčä aytmış munı (DTS,632) In Rabguzi's work "Qisa Rabguzi", this word means "time", "time, era". Alisher Navoi assigned the following meanings to the analyzed appropriation: 1) "opportunity":...ul vaqt zuhdu taqvog'a ne e'tibor va xushu xiradg'a ne ixtiyor (MQ,24); 2) "life": Tavba muj rim bandaning vaqti ko'zgunin isyon zangidan oritur (MQ,6); 3) "certain time" Bir necha vaqtdin so'ngra bu faqr ham Mavloni xizmatig'a musharraf bo'lub...(MQ,39); 4) "sometimes, in due time": Tabiiy dushman vaqte do'st bo'lg'aykim, suv o'tni o'churmagay va yel tufrog'ni sovurmag'ay (MQ,91). This Arabic word has the form of time (un); It is the infinitive of the verb waqata, which means "set a deadline" and summarizes the meanings such as "time", "opportunity", "moment"(O'TEL,II,91). In the studied source, the Arabic word ghash is used in the meaning of "displeasure in the heart", "dirty, dirty", "sorrow, sorrow": Jon anga fidoki, ruh etar andin g'ash (MQ,23); Surati darveshvash va ma'nisi sarosar g'ash (MQ,34); Vujudi oltuni ul qalbu g'ashdin ayrilibon (MQ,56). At this point, it should be noted that istilah combined with the Turkish suffix formed the meaning of "defect, shortcoming": Agarchi zotida yuz nav' qalbi g'ashliq bor (MQ,56). This revolution is not mentioned in the records of the 11th-14th centuries. From this, it can be understood that the first use of the term was in the works of Hazrat Navoi.

The verb Ur- is found in Kultigin's epitaph, "Golden light" memoir, "Kutadgu bilig" and "Oguznoma" epics in the meanings of "hit", "put, throw", "write".(DTS,614) In Mahmud Koshghari's "Devon" it is used in the meaning of "to hit" (MK,I,69, "to put, to throw", "to land" (MK,I,177). The lexeme dates back to the 15th century It can be seen in the work "Mahbub ul-Qulub" that it has undergone a phenomenon of meaning expansion: 1) "to hit": Va goh junun mahallasida arzol bo'ynumg'a silliy urdilar (MQ,7); 2) "distribute, spread": Va nazimlarida har she'r bila ishq o'tin olamg'a urubturlar (MQ,51); 3) "throw, throw" Olim kerakki, o'z ilmining poya va miqdorin asrag'ay, gavharni imtihon uchun toshqa urmag'ay (MQ,80-81); 4) "to look, face"...mutahayir turub erdi, ko'zin osmong'a urub erdi (MQ,53); 5) "stab": Yatimki pichoq urmoq aning ishi bo'lg'ay (MQ,30); ...aqrabdek nechaki yetsa nish urub (MQ,30); 6) "beat": Yonsa qo'nmoqqa tabl urar har dam (MQ,25); 7) "turn around" Muallaq urmoqlarida xoksorlig' oshkor (MQ,30). At the same time, the noun was combined with lexemes of the word group and formed the following semes: "to praise":...kalom surubturlar oni bo'z kiyizga o'xshata masal urubturlar (MQ,72); "to hunt" Arslon ishi sayd urub sibo'ni to'yg'ormoq ov qilmoq (MQ,59); "not to allow to speak, not to speak": Man' va nahy tufrog'in og'zig'a urmoq avlo. (MQ,23); "blame" Atoridg'a ta'n urmoqdur so'zining rangi.ayblamoq (MQ,54); "to hear, to pour into the ear": Piri roh va soliki ogoh mundoq durrdek takallumkim surdi, bu gavharlarni aning qulog'ig'a urdi (MQ,96); "to exaggerate":...nuqtalari hisobi bila lof urar (MQ,26); "sound, call, exhortation" Har kishiga yuz muloyamat ko'rguzdung ming g'ilzat va quduratg'a salo urmoq kerak (MQ,58); "pen, write"...varaq yuziga maorifnigor xoma urubtur (MQ,49); "to step, to ride, to walk" Va Shayx "Ollloh!" deb ul suvg'a qadam urdi va muridg'a "Boyazid", deb qadam urmoq buyurdi (MQ,88); "to shake hands to follow": Bas o'zni yaxshilar orasida yashurg'on va alar etagiga ilik urg'on yaxshiroqdur (MQ,91); "to cut off the head, cut off the neck" Eranlardin mardona gunoh vujudqa kelsa, bo'ynig'a yuklangandin so'ng bo'yin urarlar (MQ,32); "get busy": O'z muborak iliki bila ekin suvorurg'a bel urar erdi (MQ,42).

Alisher Navoi used the term "alam" in several meanings in his work "Mahbub ul-Qulub":

1) **hurt**: Yamonlarg'a lutf-u karam, yaxshilarg'a mujibi zarar va alam (MQ,66);

2) **suffering**: Bas mashaqqatkim, andin ruhg'a alam yetar (MQ,64);

3) **flame**: So'xtai firoq o'lmakdin anga g'am yo'q, anduxtai ishtiyiq kuymakdin anga alam yo'q (MQ,43);

4) **anxiety**: ...bir botmon bug'doy uchun xirmonni sovrmoqdin alami yo'q (MQ,18).

From the examples, it can be understood that the expansion of the Turkish and foreign idioms used in the work is manifested in the increase of the lexical meaning at the expense of new derivative semas. In this case, the lexical meaning of a specific word gives its name to the object, reality, action, state, sign and sensation (referent). As a result, the size of the referent expands, and the range of understanding about it increases. It can be said that words can be used in different meanings according to the different stylistic structure of the text.

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